

Protocol:

*A2.4.3: Documented example of the
leakage transfer standards test*

Work package 2

This report was written as part of activity 2.4.3 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a protocol for performance of tests of 4 different quantities in the developed transfer standards. For more details about this project, please visit www.mfmet.eu

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1. Scope

This document shall provide a protocol for the measurement of at least 4 different quantities in the transfer standards developed under task A2.4.2.

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A2.4.3 M33	CETIAT, CMI, LNE, microfluidic and IMTAG will perform a documented calibration of the transfer standards developed in A2.4.2 for the quantities identified in A2.4.1. The documented calibrations will be performed at CETIAT, LNE, microfluidic and IMTAG facilities to ensure traceability to national standards for the at least 4 quantities identified in A2.4.1.	CETIAT , CMI, LNE, microfluidic, IMTAG

2. Introduction

This protocol describes how to test 2 different types of microfluidic transfer standards. One type is a Topas chip, the other is a set of glass chips. They are described in report A2.4.4.

The laboratories will perform measurements to characterise the quantities identified in A2.4.1:

- flow rate,
- delivered volume,
- dead volume,
- dimensions,
- leakage,
- roughness,
- hydrodynamic resistance.

3. Description of the transfer standards

3.1. Glass chips

There are 8 different designs, all made on a 45x15x2 mm glass chip manufactured by IMT. Table 1 gives the general dimensions of the 2 types of channels constituting the chips. Table 2 presents the number of copies for each design. The following paragraphs pictures a photograph of an actual chip with its technical drawing, notice that the manufactured chip is in fact the symmetry of the drawn design around a vertical axis.

Table 1: general dimensions of the glass transfer standards.

Dimensions	Width (mm)	Depth (mm)	Length (mm)
Main channels (green)	1.000	0.100	≈ 40
Leakage channels (blue)	0.150	0.002	≈ 10
Inlets and outlets	0.800		

Table 2: number of copies for each design.

Design	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Number of copies	4	4	4	4	4	3	3	2

3.1.1. Design 1

Figure 1: Design 1 (4 copies), dimensions in mm.

The top main channel serves as a reference channel, that is a straight channel with no connection to any leakage channel. The two bottom main channels are connected by a single leakage channel.

3.1.2. Design 2

Figure 2: Design 2 (4 copies), dimensions in mm.

The top main channel serves as a reference channel. The two bottom main channels are connected by two identical leakage channels in parallel.

3.1.3. Design 3

Figure 3: Design 3 (4 copies), dimensions in mm.

The top main channel serves as a reference channel. The bottom main channel is divided in two sections, connected by a U-shaped leakage channel of length 10 mm.

3.1.5. Design 5

Figure 5: Design 5 (4 copies), dimensions in mm.

The top main channel serves as a reference channel. Each main channel below is divided in two sections, connected by a leakage channel of decreasing length from 15 mm to 5 mm.

Channel #3 (with the 10 mm-long leakage channel) can be compared to designs 3 and 4.

Channel #4 (with the 5 mm-long leakage channel) can be compared to design 1.

3.1.6. Design 6

The top main channel serves as a reference channel. The main channel below is connected in the middle to a 5 mm-long leakage channel, whose outlet directly opens to the atmosphere.

3.1.7. Design 7

Figure 7: Design 7 (3 copies), dimensions in mm.

The top main channel serves as a reference channel. The main channel below is connected in the middle to a 10 mm-long leakage channel, whose outlet directly opens to the atmosphere. It is similar to design 6 but the wiggly path of the leakage channel makes it twice as long.

3.1.8. Design 8

Figure 8: Design 8 (2 copies), dimensions in mm.

This special design has no reference channel. The two top leakage channels form a 45° angle with the main channel.

3.2. Polymer chips

There are also 8 different designs made of TOPAS, but they all fit on a single 75.5x25.5 mm chip manufactured by microfluidic ChipShop (MCS). MCS produced 32 copies of the chip, each containing the 8 designs. Figure 9 pictures a photograph of an actual chip with its CAD design.

Figure 9: The Topas chip (32 copies) with designs 1 to 8 (from left to right).

Each design of the polymer transfer standards is built in a similar way: two parallel main channels connected by a leakage channel of smaller dimensions (Figure 10). Mini-Luer interfaces are located at each end of the main channels to serve as inlets or outlets. The main channels have the same dimensions, with a width of 0.5 mm and a length of 17.5 mm. Table 3Table 1 gives the dimensions of the leakage channel for each design on the Topas chip.

To ensure the leakage channel will only affect the flow and the measurements due to the change of dimensions, its path is always made of the same number of turns at the same angle.

Figure 10: Detail of a single design on the polymer chip.

Table 3: Dimensions of the leakage channel for each design of a Topas transfer standard.

Design	Width (mm)	Depth (mm)	Length (mm)
1	0.100	0.100	40
2	0.050	0.050	40
3	0.020	0.020	40
4	0.010	0.010	40
5	0.050	0.050	20
6	0.020	0.020	20
7	0.010	0.010	20
8	0.005	0.005	20

4. Test protocol for the glass transfer standards

4.1. Testing schedule

The glass transfer standards are circulating between all laboratories. One spare copy of each design is kept at CETIAT in case of transport or testing hazard, or to repeat a test on a pristine copy at the end of the comparison in case of doubt.

Table 4 presents the time periods when the chips are expected to be tested by each laboratory. It also indicates which quantities are planned to be measured by the partners, and which chip are concerned.

Table 4: Matrix of experiments for the measured quantities on the glass transfer standards (version of February 29th, 2024, not the actual dates of measurements for the last partners).

	Glass transfer standards	Design Copy	1			2			3			4			5			6		7		8	Number of tests
			1-1	1-2	1-3	2-1	2-2	2-3	3-1	3-2	3-3	4-1	4-2	4-3	5-1	5-2	5-3	6-1	6-2	7-1	7-2	8-1	
October	LNE	dimensions	x	x	x	x			x			x			x			x		x		10	
		roughness*	?			?			?			?			?			?		?		?	0
early November	IPQ	delivered volume*	x	x	x	x			x			x			x			x		x		10	
		dead volume*	x	x	x	x			x			x			x			x		x		10	
		flow rate	x			x			x			x											4
late November	CEA	dimensions	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	?	?	x	?	?	x	?	x	?	x	14	
early December	DTI	flow rate	x						x	x	x	x	x	x								7	
		hydro. resistance	x	x	x	x			x	x	x	x			x			x		x		x	12
January	TUBITAK UME	<i>postponed</i>																				0	
late February	University of Glasgow	dimensions	x			x						x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	12	
		flow rate	x			x			x			x			x			x	x	x	x	x	9
		leakage**			?					?													0
mid March	CETIAT	hydro. resistance	x			x	x	x	x			x	x	x	x			x	x	x	x	13	
		leakage**		x			x			x			x			x			x		x		7
early April	FDA	dimensions	?			?			?			?			?			?		?	?	?	0
		flow rate	x			x			x			x			x	x	x	x		x	x	x	11
		hydro. resistance													x	x	x			x	x	x	6
		leakage**	x			x			x			x			x			x		x		x	8
late April	TUBITAK UME	flow rate	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x			x			x		x		12	
May or later	RISE	flow rate	<i>to be defined (experiments as part of EURAMET pilot study 1613 and not in the scope of MFMET A2.4.3)</i>																		0		
		hydro. resistance																					0
			13	7	6	12	4	3	12	4	3	13	4	3	12	4	3	11	4	12	3	12	

version: 2024-02-29

* test performed by only one laboratory

** potentially destructive test

4.2. Identification of the chips

The chips are identified in Table 4 using the following format:

“design number – copy number”

On the actual chips, the number of bars done with a permanent marker on both long sides corresponds to the copy number. The design can always be identified with the channels' configuration. Figure 11 shows an example with chip 1-3 (3 black bars).

Figure 11: Identification of chip 1-3 (design 1 – copy 3).

The spare copies kept at CETIAT are pristine, without any marking on the sides.

4.3. Comments on the testing matrix

The goal of these tests is to check two types of reproducibility:

1) Manufacturing reproducibility between copies

For each quantity, one laboratory checks the reproducibility of the manufacturing of one design by testing all copies of the same design. Ideally, this should be done with pristine copies, in case water stays trapped in the micro channels from tests to tests for instance, which would introduce external uncertainty on the chip's manufacturing reproducibility (see cleaning protocol in 4.4.3).

2) Measurement reproducibility between laboratories

For each quantity (and ideally each design), all laboratories test the same copy.

It would be interesting to check for drift over time. However, this test must be done by the “first” participant, which depends on the quantity. Depending on the remaining time available at the end of the tests, this subject will be discussed after completion on the initial testing matrix.

4.4. Measuring the quantities of interest

4.4.1. Dimensions

The objective of this protocol is to determine the following dimensional parameters:

- The width and length of the main and leakage channels.
- The diameter of the holes located at the ends of each main channel or leakage channel used as connectors.
- The depth of the channels, when possible.

The references to each measured parameter are presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Identification of the dimensional parameters to be measured.

Most of the channels are linear but designs 3, 4, 7 and 8 present channels with curves (U, L or more complex shapes). Specific analysis tools will be needed to measure the non-linear channels. As these specific methods may differ depending on the laboratory, they must be documented by the partners in their own report.

The measurement of depth was measured by IMT on the open devices during manufacturing, but measuring this parameter once the channels are closed is challenging. Some methods used by the partners might not even be able to determine this characteristic.

It is advised to repeat each measurement three times at different points in the channels and holes. The calculated standard deviation σ_r therefore represents both the repeatability of the measurement and the inhomogeneity of the patterns. Each measurement is associated to a type-uncertainty u_c calculated as follows:

$$u_c = \sqrt{\sigma_r^2 + \sigma_c^2}$$

Where σ_c denotes the uncertainty of the calibration.

Results can be presented in a table such as Table 5.

Table 5: Example to present the dimensions measurements.

Design n	Hole 1		Hole 2		Width		Length	
	Diam.	u_c	Diam.	u_c	Meas.	u_c	Meas.	u_c
Channel 1								
Channel 2								
Channel 3								
Leakage channel								

4.4.2. Roughness

The measurements of the roughness on the microfluidic devices using Atomic Force Microscope were performed with the following instructions:

- For open-loop systems (without a servo system), scanning must be initiated before measurement. For open loop systems (without a servo system), the scan must be started before the measurement. A thermalization step of a few hours is recommended to avoid drift of the piezoelectric ceramics.
- If the system has a protective housing, it must be closed.
- It is recommended to wait at least one hour before starting measurements to allow the system to stabilise thermally (instrument, tip, sample).
- It is requested to work around the neutral point on the scanner (zero supply voltage)
- The X-axis of the grid should be aligned with the axis of the lever.
- The fast scan axis must be parallel to the lever axis.
- Depending on the Z-axis, the resolution should be adjusted as best as possible by the user.
- The servo control of the tip should be optimised by the user.
- The installation of the roughness measurement system must be free of vibrations.
- The AFM tip should have a sufficiently small radius of curvature to follow the surface topography.
- The scan size and image resolution (number of pixels per scan line) should be adjusted.

Determining the surface roughness and its homogeneity requires a minimum of 5 measurements, changing the area between each measurement.

To calculate the roughness S_a , it is necessary to use image processing software. The processing steps to be carried out are generally the following:

- Extraction of the topographic image (calibrated).
- Straightening of the topographic image.
- Sequencing as close to the surface as possible to eliminate any contamination on the surface.

Such measurements have been performed on glass open sample specifically designed for AFM measurements but could not be performed on transfer standard samples. In fact, only polymer devices were available in open version, but the channels were not large enough to put the system (tip + cantilever + chip) in the bottom. As the glass transfer standard samples were not open, the measurement cannot be done.

4.4.3. Setup for flow quantities

Check the chip for blockage with dry compressed air in the main and leakage channels. Connect the outlet of the chip to a tube immersed in (clean) water and check for air bubbles.

Clean and purge the setup with ethanol.

Before starting the measurements, make sure all the connectors are leak-tight, using preferably screwed connectors (Upchurch for instance).

4.4.4. Volume

The following protocol can be applied to measure the total volume of:

- Each channel separately
- The full system.

Using a calibrated weighing scale (Figure 13), the volume is determined gravimetrically by weighing the chip to be calibrated when empty and when filled with a suitable liquid of known density. The

difference obtained in the weighing measurements gives the mass of the liquid contained in a particular channel.

In the case the weighing scale requires a minimum load, the chip to be measured can put on top of a standard weight and then subtract the mass of the standard weight alone (Figure 14).

After weighing the chip when empty and dry, the channel to be measured must be filled with a liquid of known density, for instance ultra-pure degassed water. To only measure the volume of the channel, the drops at each outlet of the channel caused by surface tension above the surface of the chip must be carefully removed, by means of an absorbing tissue or a plastic card to scrap the drop. Take care the capillary forces don't pull liquid out of the channel.

To refer to the channels, it is proposed to start from the reference main channel and name them in descending order, as in Figure 15 or Figure 12.

Figure 13: Example of a weighing scale, s used for volume calibration.

Figure 14: The chip to be weighed can be accompanied by a standard weight if the scale requires a minimum load.

Figure 15: Common notation to name the channels of the chips.

The volume of a microfluidic channel can be determined gravimetrically according to the formula described in ISO 4787:

$$V_{20} = (I_L - I_E) \times \frac{1}{\rho_L - \rho_A} \times \left(1 - \frac{\rho_0}{\rho_B}\right) \times [1 - \gamma(t - 20)] \quad (8)$$

Where:

- V_{20} Volume at a reference temperature of 20 °C
- I_L Balance indication of the vessel with the contained liquid
- I_E Balance indication of the vessel with empty vessel
- ρ_L Density of liquid
- ρ_A Density of air
- ρ_0 Density at reference conditions for weighing, 1.2 kg/m³
- ρ_B Density of standard weights
- t Temperature

γ Coefficient of cubical thermal expansion of the material which the chip tested is made of

Each channel is tested separately. The difference obtained in the weighing measurements gives the mass of the liquid contained in a particular channel. At least 5 tests should be performed in order to obtain the measurement repeatability.

The uncertainty of the volume measurements is determined according to EURAMET guide cg 19.

4.4.5. Hydrodynamic resistance

4.4.5.1. Interest of each design

The goal of the chips' variety of designs is to compare the hydrodynamic resistance behaviour for typical microfluidic paths geometries:

- **Design 1** serves as a reference to measure the hydrodynamic resistance R_{leak} through one leakage channel of a given length l .
- **Design 5** serves to verify the additivity of the resistivity. For a leakage channel of length $n \times l$, the total resistivity should be $n \times R_{\text{leak}}$.
- **Design 2** serves to verify the additivity of the conductivity (inverse of the resistivity). For n identical leakage channels in parallel, the equivalent resistivity should verify:

$$\frac{1}{R_{\text{eq}}} = \frac{1}{n \times R_{\text{leak}}}$$

- Comparing **design 3** with the straight channel of same length in design 5 makes it possible to evaluate the contribution of a bend to the hydrodynamic resistance.
- Comparing **design 4** with the straight channel of same length in design 5 makes it possible to evaluate the contribution of multiple tight bends (wiggly path) to the hydrodynamic resistance.
- **Design 6** serves to evaluate the flow-dependency of the leakage rate for punctual leak type outside of a main channel.
- Comparing **design 7** with the straight and shorter channel of design 6 makes it possible to evaluate the contribution of the added length and wiggly path to the hydrodynamic resistance.
- **Design 8** serves to compare the leakage flow rate (for the same inlet pressure) given the flow direction and the angle of the leakage channel.

4.4.5.2. Tests to be performed

Setpoints:

- Use preferably a pressure-controlled flow generator with the following inlet pressure setpoints: 100, 200, 500, 1000, 2000 mbar (relative to the outlet)
- Otherwise, determine the flow rate setpoints for which you obtain the corresponding inlet pressure. They are probably within a range of 10 to 1000 $\mu\text{L/h}$. The flow rate setpoints will depend on the configuration of the channels!

For each setpoint, measure the inlet pressure (or differential pressure) AND the flow rate:

- In each main channel separately
- In the leakage channel

See 4.4.5.3 for a description of the flow configurations and how to reference them. Make sure the full configuration is purged of air and filled in with water before performing the measurement (see 4.4.5.4.2).

Repeat each measurement 2 times (3 measurements in total per setpoint).

Figure 16 shows the general setup for the equipment.

Figure 16: setup for the measurement of hydrodynamic resistance.

4.4.5.3. Matrix of flow configurations

Configurations are referenced with the number of the corresponding design and a letter. Arrows indicate the inlet and outlet. The X indicate the holes that must be closed. In general, there should be only one inlet and one outlet. The exceptions are configurations 6C, 7C and 8B to 8E, for which a second a flowmeter is required to measure the two outlets simultaneously (if this is not possible, measurement should be done on one outlet while leaving the other open before switching the flowmeter to the other outlet).

Most designs only have a couple of *main* configurations that must be measured (section 4.4.5.3.1). However, in case other configurations are measured to check the chips have indeed the same behaviour with a reversed flow or a symmetrical mounting, *bonus* configurations are also presented with a dedicated letter for easier reference in the report of each laboratory (section 4.4.5.3.2).

Table 6: comments on the various flow configurations (the ones in black are mandatory).

Design 1	
Configuration 1A	
Configuration 1B	
Configuration 1C	Bonus configurations
Configuration 1D	
Configuration 1E	
Configuration 1F	
Configuration 1G	
Configuration 1H	
Design 2	
Configuration 2A	
Configuration 2B	
Configuration 2C	Bonus configurations
Configuration 2D	
Configuration 2E	
Configuration 2F	
Configuration 2G	
Configuration 2H	
Design 3	
Configuration 3A	
Configuration 3B	Bonus configuration

Design 4	
Configuration 4A Configuration 4B	
Configuration 4C Configuration 4D Configuration 4E Configuration 4F Configuration 4G Configuration 4H	Bonus configurations
Design 5	
Configuration 5A Configuration 5B Configuration 5C	
Design 6	
Configuration 6A Configuration 6B Configuration 6C	<i>Requires two flowmeters</i>
Design 7	
Configuration 7A Configuration 7B Configuration 7C	<i>Requires two flowmeters</i>
Design 8	
Configuration 8A Configuration 8B Configuration 8C Configuration 8D Configuration 8E	<i>Require two flowmeters, one downstream of each outlet</i>

4.4.5.3.1. Main configurations

Figure 17: main configurations for design 1.

Expected results:

$$R_{2A} = R_{\text{main}}$$

$$R_{2B} = R_{\text{main}} + \frac{1}{\frac{1}{R_{\text{leak}}} + \frac{1}{R_{\text{leak}}}}$$

Figure 18: main configurations for design 2.

Expected results:

$$R_{3A} = 2.1 R_{\text{main}} + 2 R_{\text{leak}}$$

length of reference channel: 39 mm
 $((39-2) + 6 + 39) / 39 \approx 2.1$

Figure 19: main configurations for design 3.

Expected results:

$$R_{4A} = R_{\text{main}}$$

$$R_{4B} = R_{\text{main}} + 2 R_{\text{leak}} + R_{\text{bends}}$$

Figure 20: main configurations for design 4.

Expected results:

$$R_{5A} \approx 0.62 R_{\text{main}} + 3 R_{\text{leak}}$$

$$R_{5B} \approx 0.74 R_{\text{main}} + 2 R_{\text{leak}}$$

$$R_{5C} \approx 0.87 R_{\text{main}} + R_{\text{leak}}$$

Figure 21: main configurations for design 5.

Expected results:

$$R_{6A} = R_{\text{main}}$$

$$R_{6B} = 0.5 R_{\text{main}} + R_{\text{leak}}$$

Comment: 2 flowmeters needed, one downstream of each outlet

Figure 22: main configurations for design 6.

Figure 23: main configurations for design 7.

Figure 24: main configurations for design 8.

4.4.5.3.2. Bonus configurations

Expected results: $R_{1A} = R_{1C} = R_{1D} = R_{1E}$

$R_{1B} = R_{1F} = R_{1G} = R_{1H}$

Figure 25: bonus configurations for design 1.

Expected results: $R_{2A} = R_{2C} = R_{2D} = R_{2E}$

$R_{2B} = R_{2F} = R_{2G} = R_{2H}$

Figure 26: bonus configurations for design 2.

Expected results:

$$R_{3B} = R_{3A}$$

Figure 27: bonus configurations for design 3.

Figure 28: bonus configurations for design 4.

4.4.5.4. Recommendations

4.4.5.4.1. Measurement of the inlet pressure

The position of the pressure sensor relatively to the chip should be precisely reported in case the influence of the installation is not negligible compared to the pressure drop caused by the chip.

In addition to the measurements with the chip, it is suggested to measure the inlet pressure without the chip to cancel out the influence of the installation.

4.4.5.4.2. Air purging before the measurement

Before performing the measurement in any recommendation, it is recommended to purge the air out of the channels. While it is straightforward in the case of a single-outlet configuration, it might need several steps in cases such as design 1. Figure 29 suggests an example for a purging protocol.

Figure 29: recommendation for purging air out of the chip before measuring flow quantities.

4.4.5.5. Computing the hydrodynamic resistance

If the pressure drop of the chip is measured directly with differential pressure sensor ΔP connected to the inlet and the outlet of the chip, the hydrodynamic resistance of the chip $R_H(\text{chip})$ is directly computed as the slope of the linear regression of ΔP as a function of the flow rate Q .

If only the inlet pressure upstream of the chip is measured by the pressure sensor (Figure 16), the slope of the linear regression corresponds to the sum of the resistance of the chip and the resistance of everything downstream of the chip: $R_H(\text{chip}) + R_H(\text{downstream})$

To compensate for the additional resistance, the measurements must be repeated with the same setup and over the same range of flow rates but without the chip, so that $R_H(\text{downstream})$ can be evaluated with a similar linear regression. Subtracting the two computed slopes thus yields the hydrodynamic resistance of the chip alone $R_H(\text{chip})$.

The uncertainty associated with the hydrodynamic resistance must take into account the following components:

- Uncertainty of the pressure measurements
- Uncertainty of the flow rate measurements
- Uncertainty of the linear regression
- Uncertainty of any additional operation (such as the subtraction of the two slopes in the case of a non-differential pressure measurement).

4.4.6. Flow rate

The same protocol as for hydrodynamic resistance can be applied. The only difference, for a laboratory that is involved only in measuring the flow rate, is that the setpoints may be defined as flow rates instead of inlet pressures. The interest of this setup is to check how the chip affects the flow rate compared to the usual behaviour of the setup for nominal values of the flow generator. A pressure sensor should still be present at the inlet of the chip, although its accuracy is less critical. It should also be recorded, at least to check the pressure in case a burst happens.

Provided there are enough flowmeters to measure the flow rates downstream of each outlet, an additional protocol could be to compare the flow rate coming out the main channel (directly from the inlet) to the sum of the flow rates coming out of the other main channel, after passing through the leakage channel.

5. Test protocol for the polymer transfer standards

5.1. Testing schedule

Because polymer is not as durable as glass, it was decided that each partner would use their own copies of the chips instead of circulating the same set from partner to partner. Out of the 32 copies available, 4 copies were sent to each partner for parallel testing (Table 7).

Table 7: Distribution of the polymer transfer standards

Copies	Partner
1 to 4	LNE
5 to 8	IPQ
9 to 12	CEA
13 to 16	TUBITAK UME
17 to 20	DTI
21 to 24	University of Glasgow
25 to 28	FDA
29 to 32	CETIAT

5.2. Identification of the chips

The polymer transfer standards were individually sealed. To protect them during transportation it was decided to keep the packaging intact. Thus, the identification of the chips has only been written on the plastic wrap with a number from 1 to 32. Each partner should keep track of the chip used and note its reference during the measurement.

Figure 30: Sealed Topas chip with its identification number written on the packaging.

5.3. Measuring the quantities of interest

5.3.1. Dimensions

The goal is to measure the width and length of the main and leakage channels. Figure 31 presents the identification numbers for each channel to report the results. This protocol is similar to the one for the glass transfer standards presented in section 4.4.1.

Figure 31: Identification of the channels on the polymer transfer standard.

5.3.2. Roughness

The same protocol as 4.4.2 for the glass chips can be applied.

5.3.3. Setup for flow quantities

Check the chip for blockage with dry compressed air in the main and leakage channels. Connect the outlet of the chip to a tube immersed in (clean) water and check for air bubbles.

As the chip are pristine for each partner, no cleaning should be needed. If needed, however, it is recommended to only use pure water, as ethanol might damage the polymer.

Before starting the measurements, make sure all the connectors are properly fitted and leak-tight.

5.3.4. Volume

The protocol is identical to the one for glass chips presented in 4.4.4.

5.3.5. Hydrodynamic resistance

The goal of the chips' variety of designs is to compare the hydrodynamic resistance dependence to the dimensions of the leakage channel, all main channels being identical:

- **Design 1 to 4:** identical length of the leakage channel, with decreasing cross section
- **Design 5 to 8:** identical length of the leakage channel, but twice as short as designs 1 to 4, with decreasing cross section.
- The pairs of designs 2-5, 3-6 and 4-7 respectively have the same cross sections but with different lengths (see Table 3 in 3.2 for the exact values).

The principle of the measurements is the same as described in 4.4.5, but only with the configurations of the glass design 1 (Figures 17 and 25) applied to each design of the polymer chip. For any polymer design (see Figure 32 for instance), water can flow:

- **Configuration a:** only through a main channel (top left to top right, other outlets closed)
- **Configuration b:** through the combination of both main channels and the leakage channel (top left to bottom right, other outlets closed)
- **Configuration c:** only through the leakage channel (bottom left to top right, other outlets closed)
- **Configuration d:** through the combination of one main channel and the leakage channel (top left to bottom left, other outlets closed)

Figure 32: Detail of one design from the polymer transfer standard.

5.3.6. Flow rate

The protocol for the polymer chips is identical to the one for the glass chips, see 4.4.6.

6. Description of the report to be submitted by each laboratory

6.1. Description of the test

The tests must be described in an understandable manner and according to the procedures developed in previous tasks. Indicate the methods that are used and the reference documents.

6.2. Measurand

The physical quantity to be measured must be described in detail as well as any factors influencing the measurand(s), e.g. liquid.

Examples are:

- Differential pressure between the inlet and outlet of a microfluidic device at a given flow rate of a liquid with well-known characteristics.
- Volume flow rate of demineralized water at 20 °C measured upstream of the microfluidic device (object under test).

6.3. Test method

The test method must be described in a technical manner. If possible, references to existing methods, standards, calibration guides, or any other publication (preferably available online) should be included in this section. At minimum, this section should include a description of the instrument(s) needed to perform the test. In this case, this section can include parts (or refer to) of the instrument(s) operating manual supplied by the manufacturer.

6.4. Setup and test equipment

A detailed description of the setup, standards, and other relevant equipment to be used for a given test or set of tests must be given. It could be a schematic description with explicit information about each element of the setup. The type of equipment or standard, accuracy, relevant specifications, and the description of how each equipment should be used.

Moreover, the position of each equipment related to the measurement of the measurand(s) must be stated, if relevant. Example: reference pressure is measured upstream the device.

6.5. Test conditions

The necessary ambient conditions, required for the operation of the instrument(s) in their operating range, can be stated in this section.

6.6. Preparation

This section should include the description of the preparation of the instrument(s), the fluid (or sample) and the operating conditions. For example: power on the instrument at least 30 minutes before operation, prepare a volume of 20 mL of ultra-pure water and set it at rest at 20 °C for at least 1 hour, etc.

6.7. Test procedure

This section shall describe all the steps to perform the measurement in the chronological order and with numbered bullets. If possible, pictures, schematics, screen captures should be present for each step so that the operator can quickly perform the step without reference to other documents or other pages in the document. A colour code can be used for different paragraphs in the step's description, with colours referring to different instruments, for example. Information on the number of repetitions of the test should be provided.

6.8. Calculation model

The equation for the measurand determination should be stated in this section, with a clear description of each of the equation's parameters, including all constants and variables. If possible, all constants' description should include associated expanded uncertainties (at $k=2$).

6.9. Uncertainty of test equipment

An uncertainty budget of each test method shall be determined according to the GUM, including the repeatability value.

It shall be calculated with a coverage factor of 2 corresponding to a coverage probability of 95 % (also stated as “ $k=2$ ”). More information on other probability calculation procedures can be found in the GUM.

7. Comparison of the results

For each quantity, the results obtained by the laboratories will be compared using the normalized error statistic E_n defined below.

If **two participants** are performing the same test, the normalized error is defined as:

$$E_n = \frac{V_{\text{lab } 1} - V_{\text{lab } 2}}{\sqrt{U_{\text{lab } 1}^2 + U_{\text{lab } 2}^2}}$$

with:

- $V_{\text{lab } i}$ the measured value of laboratory i
- $U_{\text{lab } i}$ the uncertainty of laboratory i .

The laboratories results are in agreement if $|E_n| \leq 1$.

If **three or more participants** are performing the same test, the result of each participant can be compared to the reference value (defined as the average of all the values for instance) using a slightly different formula:

$$E_{n,i} = \frac{V_{\text{lab } i} - V_{\text{ref}}}{\sqrt{U_{\text{lab } i}^2 - U_{\text{ref}}^2}}$$

The results of laboratory i are in agreement with the reference if $|E_{n,i}| \leq 1$.

8. Additional information

8.1. Customs

Glass transfer standards:

- HS Code: 90279000
- Manufacturer reference: 1398585

Topas transfer standards:

- HS Code: 39219090
- Manufacturer reference: 1575
- Article number: 30002387
- Lot: LI131587

8.2. Shipping costs

Each laboratory supports the costs to send the chips to the next laboratory.